

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: POLOYA****FIRST NAME: MOSES****PROGRAM CODE: MIPH****COURSE CODE: ACA-401****PERIOD NUMBER: 1****INSTRUCTOR: PROF. CLEENEWERCK**

Edit or delete text to show actual information below:The author applied US UK conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.

The author used Turabian (in-text/parenthetical)

The author did did *not* use Zotero to insert referencesThe author did did *not* use Grammarly Premium (EUCLID provides access)

The author used the following software: (e.g., MSWord 2016 on Windows 8)

INTEGRAL FACETS OF ACADEMIC WRITING

1) INTRODUCTION

My reflection after reading the EUCLID coursepack for period one and having listened to the video clip on effective academic writing is that at EUCLID, a concise step by step standards are provided to students in the form of learning materials and short videos to facilitate the learning process. Broadly, an academic paper must comprise of an introduction, the body and conclusion (EUCLID 2015, 4). While it is critically important to use acceptable standards in writing an academic essay, with a focus on the question, and or thesis to be answered, the approach and style matters a lot to readers (EUCLID 2015, 6). Ideas or argument has to be brought out very clearly and written using appropriate techniques and acceptable writing style without plagiarism (EUCLID 2015, 8).

Plagiarism is a serious violation of academic honesty, it involves copying and pasting, word by word transcription, quoting, and paraphrasing someone's words or ideas without citation or quotation marks (EUCLID 2015, 10). This has multiple implications; it reduces the quality of an academic paper as readers will not be able to verify or confirm factual information presented in the paper, failure of an assignment, grade reduction, course failure, suspension as well as dismissal from academic institution (EUCLID 2015, 12). In this response paper I would like to agree that plagiarism is a serious academic offense and it further provides the characteristics and major considerations when writing an academic essay.

2) TRAITS OF ACADEMIC ESSAY

The quality of academic essay is dependable on the text method including citations, notes, references and the writing style utilized. In the EUCLID context, an excellence academic paper starts from the use of a EUCLID standard word template that provides for styles, font size, grammar, and spacing among others (EUCLID 2015, 42). These parameters are used by academicians or any other readers to determine how good and authentic the paper is. The EUCLID ACA – 401 coursepack in pages 43-51 provides some rules of thumb for writing academic papers or publications and the fundamentals of grammar as a basic aspect of quality academic paper. It stems from identification of the topic, question or thesis to be answered, researching through the questions, writing the essay, referencing or citing relevant information and editing before submission (EUCLID 2015, 2).

Most academic writings are drawn from the work of other writers or researchers. Therefore, to gather the necessary information to form the body of the writing, one has to extensively research on the topic using credible academic sources that will provide evidence and support to the argument or discussion (EUCLID 2015, 3). This also involves consulting as many reading materials as possible, writing down important aspects of every information that relates to the topic, combining it with creative and critical thinking that will enable the writer to broaden ideas and at the same time narrow the focus or scope of ideas to ensure the essay is well balanced. It is important to remember that while reading any credible material, making note of sources of information are critical (EUCLID 2015, 3). The bibliographic details of every material read has to be recorded down including the author, date, title, publisher, and the place of publication as well as volume and issue numbers for journal articles. This helps in making appropriate in-text citation and list of references (EUCLID 2015, 34).

Plagiarism is a serious academic offense that every academic writer should avoid through referencing (EUCLID 2015, 9). Using any information without giving credits to the writer is plagiarism except for ideas that are considered general knowledge (EUCLID 2015, 31). Therefore, as writers one of our duty is to guide readers through the text, and be consistent with one of the quote and citation styles that will help the readers to make connections, access source documents and verify, if necessary, the validity of our arguments giving evidence on which they are based; but most importantly, good referencing is essential to avoid any possible accusation of plagiarism (EUCLID 2015, 13). Citation style differs, depending on the aim of our work but the purpose is the same, three major methods exist; in-text citations, list of works cited and footnote referencing (EUCLID 2015, 15).

In-text citations

This refers to citing the piece of work being used within the text itself. It involves indicating the author's name in parenthesis followed by the page number where the information came from (EUCLID 2015, 16). This method is also applicable when using quotations or paraphrasing by use of quotation marks to reflect what the original author of

the information has stated (EUCLID 2015, 18). However, when the quotations are long, for example four or more lines, it will take no quotation marks but rather indented and looks like a separate little paragraph. It is important to note that the use of quotations or paraphrasing in academic writing be limited otherwise it would dilute the research paper. Most importantly it should be used when there is a strong language in the quote that emphasizes the meaning of a particular information or when an authority figure says something that can help the writer persuades the readers (EUCLID 2015, 22).

Bibliography

This refers to the references listed at the end of the book or paper. It provides publication information for each of the sources that has been cited in the paper (EUCLID 2015, 33). This approach uses specific formats as described below;

For books and online books, the list of references should take in the format below;

Authors Name. Book Title. (Place of Publication: Publisher, Date). For example

Gerson, Steven. *Technical Communication Process and Product*. (Upper Saddle River: Pearson, 2009). 34

For a website;

Author. Title of the site, name of any editor listed, and the URL in brackets (<URL>). For example;

Lisa Schlein. *UN: Most Child, Maternal Deaths Occur in Sub-Saharan Africa*. (<https://www.voanews.com/africa/un-most-child-maternal-deaths-occur-sub-saharan-africa>). Accessed Oct 2019.

Footnote referencing

Finally, to avoid plagiarism one can also use footnote referencing. This is done by making citation either in sentences between quotation marks or as a separate paragraph using the quote style (EUCLID 2015, 36). Numberings are automatically generated after the initial insertion of the footnote reference in the footnote referencing area. Just like for all the other citations methods, footnote referencing also requires that a standard format and consistent writing style is maintained throughout the paper (EUCLID 2015, 37). For example, footnote referencing takes in the format below;

Authors Name. Book Title. (Place of Publication: Publisher, Date), Page Number

Perkins, John. *Understanding Assessment*. (London: Pengium, 2008), 78. 37

Whereas bibliography does not take in to account the page number from which an information has been extracted, the footnote referencing takes in the page number while

providing citations towards the end of the sentence (EUCLID 2015, 38). It is important to note that if footnote referencing is used in a paper, the writer does not need to add work cited or references at the end of the paper. In wrapping up this section, EUCLID requires that academic writers make citations with all papers written independently but not with supervised exams, only one citation is recommended for Response Papers/Journals and 2-3 citations in a mid-term or final exams (EUCLID 2015, 38).

3) CONCLUSION

Broadly, an academic paper must comprise of an introduction, the body and conclusion (EUCLID 2015, 4). An excellence academic paper starts from the use of a EUCLID standard word template that provides for styles, font size, grammar, and spacing among others (EUCLID 2015, 42). Plagiarism is a serious academic offense that every academic writer should avoid through referencing. Other than general information, taking someone else's ideas or words such as word by word transcription, copying and pasting from the internet, quoting and paraphrasing without giving credits to the writer is plagiarism. At EUCLID, academic writers must avoid plagiarism by using any of the three acceptable forms of referencing, namely; (1) in-text citations, (2) bibliography, and (3) footnote referencing. Whereas in-text citation takes in the author's name in parenthesis followed by the page number where the information came from, the other two methods take into consideration more information including; Author's Name. Book Title. (Place of Publication: Publisher, Date). Distinctively, footnote referencing goes beyond the publisher and year of publication but also involves indicating the page number of where the information came from at the end. The use of these standard methods in a consistent manner allows the reader to access and verify the source documents, and if necessary, add weight to claimed comments and arguments; moreover, a well referenced essay will avoid any possible accusation of plagiarism. Therefore, an excellence academic essay is one that is well composed and has considered acceptable text method including citations, notes, references and the writing styles.

REFERENCES

1. Euclid University. 2015. *ACA-401 Coursepack: Period 1*. Retrieved from: <https://euclid.egnyte.com/dl/CUEsEiHd7B/ACA-401%20Coursepack.pdf> (Sept 2019).

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. *ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1*. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.